

BANGLADESH'S HEALTHCARE SECTOR COMING OF AGE

*Reform, Resilience, & Innovation converge to create the
next investment hub*

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Abbreviations

API	Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient
BIDA	Bangladesh Investment Development Authority
BDHA	Bangladesh Digital Health Architecture
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CBU	Completely Built-Up
CKD	Completely Knocked Down
CRO	Contract Research Organization
DGHS	Directorate General of Health Services
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EPZ	Export Processing Zone
EZ	Economic Zone
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GHS	Global Health Security
HSD	Health Services Division
IVD	In Vitro Diagnostics
LDC	Least Developed Country
LMIC	Lower-Middle-Income Country
MAC	Middle and Affluent Class
MHRA	Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
MIS	Management Information System
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
OT	Operation Theatre
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
R&D	Research and Development
SKD	Semi-Knocked Down
TGA	Therapeutic Goods Administration
TRIPS	Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights
UHC	Universal Health Coverage
WHO	World Health Organization
WTO	World Trade Organization

Executive Summary

Healthcare has become one of the largest sectors of the Bangladeshi economy in terms of revenue. It has been growing at a CAGR of 10.3% since 2010, employing nearly 0.3 million people directly. Several factors are driving the growth of the healthcare sector, including an aging population, a growing middle and affluent class, and the rising proportion of non-communicable diseases. The healthcare industry of Bangladesh comprises 5 prime subsectors: Healthcare Facilities, Pharmaceuticals, Medical Equipment and Devices, Digital Healthcare and Medical Biotechnology.

The country's healthcare facilities are expanding, with private hospitals, clinics, and diagnostic centers showing strong growth. Public-private partnerships and government incentives are encouraging investments. The sector benefits from policies like tax exemptions for private hospitals outside major cities, making it an attractive market for both local and foreign investors. The ongoing need for tertiary and specialized healthcare services in urban cities and the demand for primary healthcare in rural areas enhances the sector's growth potential, positioning it as a key segment to invest in.

The pharmaceutical sector, recognized as a 'Pharmerging Market,' is projected to reach US\$6 billion in 2025 at a 12% CAGR. The industry is well known for branded generics—particularly in gastrointestinal, antibiotic, and antipyretic therapies— that quenches nearly all the domestic demand. Rising NCDs (cardiovascular, diabetes) and chronic diseases, along with an increasing elderly population (25% elderly by 2036), are fueling this growth. Burgeoning advanced manufacturing (biologics, vaccines, inhalers) and global certifications elevate the industry to a global standard. Therefore, Bangladesh remains as a key player in affordable drugs. With US\$205 million in export value in 2023–24 and an export growth rate of 8.6% CAGR, it remains as one of the resilient industry in the country.

The medical equipment and devices market is experiencing robust growth, projected to reach USD 3 billion by 2030, driven by increasing demand for medical consumables and advanced diagnostic tools. The sector is heavily reliant on imports, creating a significant opportunity for local manufacturing of medical devices, especially as the country works towards self-sufficiency in producing critical healthcare products. Investment potential exists in establishing manufacturing units for essential medical consumables, like In vitro diagnostic test kits, and low-risk health monitoring devices, and leveraging the B2C model to address the rising demand for consumables. As the health complexity increases, the demand for OT support and ICU equipment is also increasing, presenting the sector as a lucrative segment for investment with high returns.

Digital transformation is further accelerating the growth in the healthcare sector. Since COVID-19, digital health has emerged as a key area of innovation, gaining momentum as the tech-savvy youth population increasingly turns to digital solutions for healthcare access. The government's Digital Healthcare Strategy 2023–2027 aims to integrate digital tools like cloud-based Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and telehealth platforms to enhance healthcare delivery and reduce costs. This transition presents investment opportunities in cloud-based services, interoperable health systems, and remote patient monitoring. Additionally, partnerships with foreign tech companies for disease management solutions and healthcare technology innovations will be crucial in driving the sector's growth.

Another breakthrough in the healthcare sector is the emergence of the bio-economy. The global bio-economy market was valued at USD 1.55 trillion in 2024 and is expected to grow to USD 4.61 trillion by 2034, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 11.5%. With its established pharmaceutical industry and significant cost advantages in conducting clinical research, Bangladesh has the potential to emerge as a key player in the regional bio-economy, provided it makes strategic investments to leverage its strengths. The proposed Laboratory Animal House and VTD Manufacturing Project in Bangladesh aims to position the country as a hub for biopharmaceutical innovation, attracting foreign direct investment. These projects will modernize preclinical testing and vaccine/biologics manufacturing, providing world-class infrastructure and WHO-GMP-certified facilities, while fostering indigenous R&D and global partnerships. By prioritizing innovation and regulatory transparency, Bangladesh will transition from generic drug reliance to high-value biopharmaceuticals, ensuring strategic advantages for FDI in South Asia. Moreover, its biodiversity enables the development of nutraceuticals, marine biotech, and herbal innovations, positioning Bangladesh as a growing hub in the bio-economy. Additionally, the country has a skilled workforce in fields like biotechnology, pharmacy, and medicine, supporting the expansion of these industries. Bangladesh also benefits from its strategic location, offering access to a large consumer market in South Asia and China through trade agreements.

The first section of the report provides an overview of Bangladesh's macroeconomy, highlighting its immense growth potential. The second section includes an overview of the healthcare sector, including insights about market size, growth potential, workforce, and the business climate. The subsequent sections highlight the key drivers of growth for the sector and elaborate upon the investment opportunities in 5 key sub-sectors, including hospitals and infrastructure, pharmaceuticals, medical equipment and devices, digital healthcare, and medical biotechnology. The final section of the report highlights a unique opportunity for investors to tap into the health insurance market of Bangladesh and help the country achieve universal coverage.

1

Macroeconomic Overview

Bangladesh's economy has shown impressive growth in recent years, with aspirations of becoming a trillion-dollar economy within the next decade. Over the past five years, the country has achieved an average annual GDP growth rate of 5.84%, surpassing major Asian peers such as Vietnam, India, Thailand, and Indonesia. With a population of over 170 million, Bangladesh's growth rate has been approximately 1.75 times higher than that of other Lower-Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) and substantially above the global average of 2.2%

Drivers for Sustained Economic Growth

Rise in middle and affluent consumers

An ambitious young workforce

High economic resilience.

Bangladesh Leads in Economic Growth Among Major Peers

[Source: World Bank, BPCS, IMF, ADB]

Although it achieved LMIC status five years later than India, Bangladesh's GDP per capita is already surpassing that of its regional counterparts. The country aims to reach upper-middle-income status by 2031. With this rapid growth, Bangladesh is on track to hit a trillion-dollar economy by 2040, maintaining an average growth rate of around 5%, or potentially even sooner if the current growth rate persists. This growth story is fueled by some major drivers.

According to a recent HSBC report, Bangladesh is projected to become the fastest-growing consumer market globally over the next decade, ranking as the ninth-largest consumer market by 2030, surpassing the peer Asian countries. A key driver of this growth is the expanding middle- and affluent-class (MAC) population, which is expected to reach 34 million by 2025, making up 17% of the population.

[Source: HSBC Global Research]

Bangladesh also caters to a young workforce ready to create value in this high-growth landscape. The nation is home to a younger population relative to most peer economies, with a median age of 26 years, below that of Indonesia (31), India (29), Thailand (39), Vietnam (32), and the global average of 30 years. More than two-thirds of the total population is readily available to create value through employment.

Despite the global impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and the consequent measures to restrict people’s mobility through the nationwide lockdown, Bangladesh shows relative macroeconomic resilience with estimated GDP growth of 5.5% in FY2020-21, followed by 3.5% in FY2019-20. Bangladesh was among the few economies with positive growth in 2020, and is ranked 40th resilient economies in the face of the COVID pandemic adversities, being the top among the South Asian nations (Bloomberg’s COVID Resilience Ranking on May 2021)

In addition to the major growth drivers, several other powerful forces underpin the remarkable expansion of Bangladesh’s economy. The country’s digital transformation is accelerating rapidly, driven by increasing mobile connectivity and a sharp rise in internet penetration. Approximately 70.1% of households use smartphones, and 50.4% have internet access (ICT survey 2024), trends that have fostered a supportive environment for the digital economy over the past decade. Concurrently, the government has prioritized a private-sector-led growth strategy, enabling the private sector to expand significantly and make strides across key industries such as healthcare, infrastructure, textiles, fintech, and fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG).

As Bangladesh continues its forward momentum driven by key growth factors, it is essential to prioritize investments in innovation and talent. Global industry leaders must recognize what sets Bangladesh apart and thus strategically plan collaborations that create a mutually beneficial environment.

2

The Healthcare Industry at a Glance

US\$14billion

Value of healthcare market (2025)

Source: BIDA

10.3% CAGR

of Healthcare Market since 2010

Source: BIDA

US\$23billion

Projection Value of healthcare market by 2030

Projected

5000+

Private & Public Healthcare Infrastructure in 2025

Source: BIDA

1,41,999

Registered Doctors as of 2023 December

Source: BM&DC

Market Overview of The Healthcare Sector

Bangladesh's healthcare sector presents one of the most promising markets in South Asia. With a projected market value of USD 23 billion by 2030, the healthcare industry is poised to expand significantly, fueled by the country's strong economic growth, increasing urbanization, and evolving healthcare needs. The sector has been experiencing a remarkable 10.3% compound annual growth rate (CAGR) since 2010, indicating sustained growth and long-term potential. Currently, there are more than 5000 public and private hospitals serving various healthcare needs of the population. Bangladesh's healthcare workforce is another critical factor in the sector's development. With over 134,000 registered doctors as of 2025, the country boasts a growing pool of medical professionals.

The growth of the healthcare sector is primarily driven by demographic, epidemiological, and health transitions. The expanding middle and affluent class population is increasingly prioritizing healthcare spending, while the rising prevalence of non-communicable diseases is further accelerating this demand. Together, these factors are creating a pressing need to modernize healthcare infrastructure and expand medical services. As a result, Bangladesh is well-positioned to emerge as a regional leader in healthcare, offering high returns on investment for those seeking to capitalize on the growing demand for healthcare services. Furthermore, the government's commitment to improving healthcare accessibility and quality, coupled with favorable investment policies, enhances the attractiveness of the sector.

3

Growth Drivers

3.1 Demographic Shift

Emerging Middle and Affluent Class Population

Bangladesh's income pyramid is rapidly reshaping, reflecting a nation on the rise. In 2018, the pyramid had a wide base: 50% of households earned less than \$1,800 annually (Bottom of the Pyramid). By 2025, this base shrinks to 30%, while the upper tiers swell—Affluent households (>\$7,800/year) triple to 5%, and the Established and Emerging Middle classes grow significantly. This upward mobility, driven by high annual GDP growth and urbanization, signals a booming middle class with rising disposable incomes. Millions are escaping poverty, creating a consumer base eager to spend on quality goods and services.

Urbanization and job creation in manufacturing and services are accelerating income growth, with household disposable income increasing in Bangladesh. By 2030, analysts predict Bangladesh's middle class will surpass 50 million, rivaling regional giants like Indonesia and Vietnam in spending power.

Higher-income means greater healthcare spending, as families prioritize wellness and chronic disease management. The expanding middle-class fuels demand for hospitals, pharmaceuticals, and digital health solutions.

Per Capita Health Expenditure (USD)

[Source: WHO]

Average Household yearly income in USD

- Affluent >7.8K
- Established 4.8K-7.8K
- Emerging Middle 3K-4.8K
- Aspirant 1.8K-3K
- Pyramid's Bottom <1.8K

Growth from 2018 to 2025E

[Source: Inspira extrapolation and projection based on BCG's "Bangladesh: The Surging Consumer Market Nobody Saw Coming" (2015), growth from 2018 to 2025E]

Percentage% of households in different income brackets in Bangladesh

Increase in life expectancy and ageing

Life expectancy in Bangladesh is increasing (65.4 years in 2000 to 73.1 in 2021) and the country's population is projected to increase to 179 million by 2030, making it one of the most densely populated nations globally.

While Bangladesh has one of the largest youth populations compared to any country in the world, this is also true that this demography, together, will enter into the age bracket above 40, where lifestyle diseases start affecting. Moreover, the number of senior citizens (60+ years) is also growing in the country. Over 15.3 million Bangladeshis are aged 60 years or above, which constitutes 9.28 percent of the total population—an increase from 7.48 percent in 2011.

An aging population and greater longevity combined will boost the demand for health services in Bangladesh as well as increasingly favor wellness and preventative services.

3.2 Epidemiological and Health Transitions

Bangladesh's health landscape is increasingly dominated by non-communicable diseases, due to environmental degradation and unsafe dietary practices. NCDs account for more than two-thirds of all deaths in Bangladesh. The country has the eighth-highest number of people with diabetes globally, affecting approximately 13.1 million individuals. Heart attacks claim the highest ~17.45% of Bangladeshi lives among all deaths. Dhaka has consistently ranked as one of the world's most polluted cities (IQAir, 2024)., exposing residents to toxic fumes. This contributes to 30% of respiratory illnesses and exacerbates cardiovascular conditions. Concurrently, a toxic food chain laced with formalin

(used for fruit preservation), carcinogenic pesticides, and adulterated oils drives a surge in cancer cases.

[Source: WHO, BBS]

Cause of Deaths in %

NCDs such as diabetes, cancer, and heart disease often require ongoing, long-term treatment and management. These conditions typically demand a bulk of medication on a monthly basis, along with frequent check-ups at specialized hospitals to monitor disease progression. The cost of treatment is compounded by the need for medical appliances that patients must use regularly at home to monitor health metrics such as glucose levels, oxygen saturation, and heart rates. Devices like glucometers, pulse oximeters, and heart rate monitors are essential for patients to track their condition and ensure that they are managing their health appropriately between hospital visits.

This growing demand for home healthcare solutions, along with the rising frequency of hospital visits for check-ups, creates an increasing need for affordable and accessible healthcare solutions, further fueling the demand for specialized medical services, equipment, and long-term pharmaceutical supplies.

3.3 Comparison of growth drivers among similar economies

Metric	Bangladesh	Vietnam	Indonesia	Sri Lanka	Nepal
Life Expectancy	73.1	73.8	68.3	76.6	70
Middle Class (% of the population -2024)	20%	13%	20%	10%	36%
Out of pocket health expenditure	74%	40%	27%	43%	51%
Share of deaths by NCD	67%	78%	52%	75%	55%

[Sources: WHO healthcare database, World Bank Data, IDF Diabetes Atlas, Wikipedia, WHO NCD profiles, UN population prospects]

Among its peer countries, particularly within a similar geographic setting, Bangladesh presents robust growth opportunities. With the second-highest percentage of middle-class population among the countries analyzed, Bangladesh's expanding middle class is increasingly ready to pay for higher-quality healthcare, creating significant opportunities for the expansion of healthcare services. Additionally, Bangladesh has the highest out-of-pocket expenditure, reflecting the ongoing growth of the private healthcare

sector and highlighting prospects for health insurance (as discussed in the later section). Moreover, the country ranks third in terms of NCD-related mortality among the compared nations, signaling a high demand for preventive care, tertiary care facilities, and medical consumables, further strengthening the case for healthcare investment.

4

Sub-sectors of Healthcare Industry

The healthcare ecosystem of Bangladesh comprises five major sub-sectors. These are differentiated by core functions (e.g., service vs. production), regulatory oversight (DGDA, MOHFW), technology reliance, and market focus. Healthcare facilities include hospitals, clinics, diagnostic centers and labs; pharmaceuticals include drug and API manufacturing, and R&D; medical equipment and devices include manufacturing of high and low tech equipment as well as devices used in both business and consumer end; digital healthcare concerns telemedicine, health IT, digital platforms; and medical biotech includes specialized bio-pharmaceuticals and its subsequent R&D and drug formulation.

Sub-sectors of the Healthcare Sector

4.1 Healthcare Facilities

Bangladesh’s health infrastructure metrics have substantially improved over the decades despite economic constraints & challenges...

Overview of Key Healthcare Facilities and Healthcare Workforce

Chart Not to Scale

[Source: Directorate General of Health Services. (2024, October 30). Health Bulletin 2023. Government of the People’s Republic of Bangladesh]

The steady growth in infrastructure, healthcare professionals, and specialized services signals a rapidly expanding healthcare sector in Bangladesh. As the demand for quality healthcare increases, the establishment of tertiary and specialized hospitals, medical education, diagnostics, and healthcare workforce training highlight the potential for future growth.

Operating on a mixed public-private model, the public system provides accessibility for low-income populations, while the private sector caters to the demand for specialized services among urban and affluent groups. Public healthcare framework is structured across four tiers: 61 national and district-level hospitals, 431 sub-district (upazila) health complexes, 1,314 union-level sub-centers, and 14,318 community clinics at the village level. Public healthcare system has limited secondary and tertiary care in key cities and focuses on primary healthcare centers in rural areas.

The private healthcare sector, catalyzed by foreign direct investment since the 1990s, now dominates inpatient care, accounting for two-thirds of the country's hospital beds. While the public system ensures accessibility for low-income groups, the private sector's growth meets the rising demand for quality and specialized services, especially among urban and affluent demographics.

Private Healthcare Infrastructure
Increased in Two Decades

Private Hospitals	4X
Clinic	3X
Diagnostic Center	6X
Dental Clinic	7X

Growth of Private Healthcare Facilities

Promising Investment Prospects

Low Bed Density Per 1,000 Population

The figure illustrates a critical gap in hospital bed availability in Bangladesh, especially when compared to its South Asian peers. Bangladesh (depicted in red) shows an increase over the years but remains **one of the lowest**, with around

0.88 beds per 1,000 population in 2021, highlighting a significant shortage. This gap between demand and supply highlights the urgent need for expanded infrastructure to meet the growing healthcare needs with increasing population.

Urban-Rural Disparity & Deficit

Rural health centers though subsidized, often lack essential equipment, medicines, and basic amenities like clean water and electricity. **Over 68% of Bangladesh's population resides in rural areas, yet only 31.7% of healthcare resources are allocated there.**

Modernization of Bangladesh's rural healthcare offers investors a compelling opportunity to transform lives and receive substantial returns, plus a **10-year corporate tax exemption for general & specialized hospitals established** outside Dhaka, Narayanganj, Gazipur and Chattogram.

Establishment of Specialized/Tertiary Hospitals and Expansion of Private-Hospital Chains

Bangladesh's healthcare sector, especially private healthcare, is expanding due to increased demand for better healthcare services. While regulations and licensing requirements exist, these are not overly prohibitive.

A notable mention can be a Tier-I Tertiary Hospital in Dhaka, which acquired capital through a prominent US Healthcare Fund and established a footprint in Bangladesh, providing specialized healthcare services. Considering the increasing demand for specialized treatments like cosmetic surgery, fertility care, or oncology, new entrants targeting niche areas can still succeed in **urban or peri-urban areas** to enhance healthcare access.

Each year, approximately USD 5 billion is spent by Bangladeshi individuals seeking medical treatment abroad. While a portion of this expenditure is directed towards advanced tertiary care, a concerning amount is spent on addressing basic healthcare needs. This creates a substantial opportunity for Bangladesh to capture this market by developing world-class tertiary care facilities and enhancing the accessibility and quality of basic healthcare services within the country. By investing in high-quality healthcare infrastructure and improving local medical services, Bangladesh can reduce the need for its citizens to seek treatment abroad, retain financial resources within the country, and make healthcare more affordable and accessible for its population.

Public-Private Partnership: Expanding Primary Healthcare

The increase in the number of community clinics from 10,723 in 2006 to 14,318 in 2023 reflects the government's commitment to broadening access to primary healthcare, particularly in rural areas. Investors can tap into the growing primary care market, especially in **underserved rural areas**, through strong incentives provided by Bangladesh government, presenting a win-win for both public health and investors.

Urgency of Scaling Medical Education and Research

Though the number of medical colleges and hospitals has increased 182% over the past two decades, highlighting the country's commitment to building a skilled healthcare workforce, still **Bangladesh's healthcare worker density was 12.8 per 10,000 population in 2024**, far below the WHO norm of 45 per 10,000. With the growing demand for healthcare professionals, there is significant potential for investors to support medical education, research centers, and training institutions, thereby raising the global benchmark of human capital in healthcare.

Government Regulation & Liberal Incentives

Bangladesh government's policies on the regulation of medical services play a significant role in shaping the market dynamics. The two incentives offered by the Bangladesh government—a 10-year corporate tax exemption for general & specialized hospitals established outside Dhaka, Narayanganj, Gazipur & Chattogram, and a 10-year corporate tax exemption to institutes providing technical training to healthcare-related skills development such as nursing, pharmacy, etc.—are clear indicators of the government's strong commitment to fostering a liberal and investment-friendly environment in the healthcare sector.

4.2 Pharmaceuticals

Key highlights of the Pharmaceutical Industry

Bangladesh is considered one of the 'Pharmerging Markets' by IQVIA in 2024. The government of Bangladesh declared it as a Thrust Sector in Industrial Policy 2016 and as an Export-Diversified Sector in Industrial Policy 2022. Pharmaceutical industry holds a projected market value of US\$6 billion in 2025 with a 12% CAGR and has grown remarkably in the past 40 years. In 1982, industry size was only BDT 1.7 billion which eventually grew more than seven hundred times by 2025.

Two effective policies have accelerated the growth of the sector. One was the Drug Control Ordinance 1982, which banned foreign companies from selling imported pharmaceutical products in Bangladesh. The other effective regulatory framework was TRIPS relaxation, which permitted Bangladesh to reverse engineer patented generic drugs. TRIPS relaxations for Bangladesh along with other LDCs were extended till December of 2032. Along with operational efficiency and continued investment by

the private sector actors, domestic production across all drug categories spurred and improved access to emergency medicines.

Tightening quality standards through adopting international certifications i.e. US-FDA, UK-MHRA, EU-EMA, Australia-TGA elevated the sector to the global stage. The sector matured into a dominant industry and now about 98% of the domestic demand is met by local manufacturers. They possess state-of-the-art manufacturing facilities, countrywide distribution network, and superior marketing team.

Bangladesh pharma market has been dominated by physician-driven branded generic products, particularly in three major therapeutic classes: Gastro-intestinal, Antibiotics and Antipyretics. As generics contribute to 90% of pharma products sold, price competitiveness and distribution efforts are two main drivers for the success of a product.

1. Growth Drivers

Shifting Disease Profile, Increasing Healthcare Spending, Growth in Health Service Delivery Channels

2. Notable Trends

Concentrated Market, Dominated by Local Players, Converging Growth Rate of Industry Leaders

3. Next Frontier

Development of Backward Linkage, R&D, Biologics, Biosimilar

Branded generic drugs currently dominate the market, comprising 80% of the drugs produced in Bangladesh. The generic segment is going to be a sought after market as it constitutes a global growth rate of 8%, and for emerging markets, it is forecasted at 9% per annum.

Disease profile in Bangladesh is being shaped in two major ways: the rise of noncommunicable diseases (NCD), and a gradual move from acute to chronic diseases. Aging population of Bangladesh is increasing, and by 2036, about 25% of Bangladeshi population will be over 50 years. Old people are more likely to be affected by four major

Projected Proportion of Population Aged over 50 Years

categories of non-communicable diseases: cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, and chronic respiratory disease. Besides, increased health consciousness among the masses has reduced the proliferation of acute diseases, while chronic diseases are expected to grow rapidly because of lifestyle changes and environmental factors.

Accessibility to drugs is expanding due to the fast growth of health service delivery channels focusing on NCDs. Apart from retail pharmacies, which will continue to be the major sales points, government and privately-owned specialized hospitals are emerging as important selling fronts for pharma products. Existing hospitals will also undergo major changes through medical infrastructure investment and becoming instrumental in establishing pharma product brands. Geographically, the industry has immense room for growth in remote corners of the country, once modern medical facilities are made available to such places in full frequency.

Pharmaceuticals Export Value from Bangladesh (USD millions)

A total of US\$205 million worth of pharmaceutical products was exported in 2023-24. It is growing at 8.6% CAGR based on the export trend of the last 5 years. Due to USAID induced budget cuts in the humanitarian sector, a few pharma manufacturers are likely to be affected at the end of FY2024-25. However, the progress up to February is satisfactory, standing at US\$145 million. Pharma

products export destinations rose from 87 to 157 countries within 11 years. The top five in this case are Sri Lanka, USA, the Philippines, Myanmar, and Kenya. LDCs are currently the most promising destinations for generic drugs.

Manufacturers boast established manufacturing capabilities for a diverse array of dosage forms, including tablets, capsules, liquid preparations, dry suspensions, injections, ointments/creams, nasal sprays, and granules. New drug formulation through R&D is at a nascent stage, with currently at least five manufacturers having initiated to diversify the products by developing facilities for producing advanced medicines like biologic drugs, vaccines, hormones, and oncology products. The sector also produces advanced drug delivery systems such as inhalers, pre-filled syringe injections, lyophilized injections, dry-powder inhalers, and sustained-release formulations, demonstrating its growing expertise in specialized and complex therapeutics. The rapid response capacity of a few manufacturers is commendable. For example, the first generic version of COVID-19 drug was launched in May 2020 and was approved by the USFDA. Along with the generics, R&D-backed export-oriented products represent one of the most promising pathways for Bangladesh's pharma sector to differentiate itself from low-cost competitors.

Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) production has been widely viewed as a crucial lever for backward integration in the industry. Bangladesh currently imports 85% of its API needs at a cost of \$1.3 billion annually, exposing manufacturers to supply disruptions and price volatility. The establishment of API parks in Munshiganj, Bagerhat, and Khulna, coupled with a draft API Policy, demonstrates a sincere national commitment to reducing this dependency. However, experts caution

that API production is fundamentally a scale game. Without massive production volumes and competitive cost structures like those in China and India, local manufacturing may fail to deliver the intended savings. For instance, Indian-produced APIs have been reported to cost 20% more than their Chinese counterparts due to scale inefficiencies. Furthermore, API manufacturing still heavily depends on imported intermediates or key starting materials (KSMs), over 70% of which India itself sources from China. While efforts to boost API production must continue, they should be selective and strategic, focusing on high-value or niche APIs that cannot be easily sourced globally, rather than pursuing blanket self-sufficiency.

Investment Opportunities

1. Establishment of Integrated Innovation Clusters

Fostering Collaborative Ecosystems through partnerships between industry, academia, and government can create hubs for formulation innovation and complex generic development. Such clusters can drive advancements in pharmaceutical technologies and attract both local and international investments.

2. Biosimilar and Biotech Joint Ventures

The *WTO TRIPS waiver, effective until 2033*, allows Bangladesh to produce generic versions of patented drugs. Utilizing this provision to attract foreign investment can build technical expertise in high-demand biologics like monoclonal antibodies and insulins.

3. Promotion of Peptide-based Therapeutics and Specialty Molecules

Encouraging the development of peptide APIs and complex molecules with a high value-to-volume ratio can position Bangladesh in specialized markets with limited global competition. Building

capabilities in small-batch, high-margin therapeutic areas such as oncology and metabolic disorders can enhance profitability and market differentiation.

4. Investment in R&D: Developing Export-Ready, Bioequivalent Products

Currently, the pharmaceutical manufacturers in Bangladesh allocate an average of 3.4% of their total annual expenditure to research and development. However, a more immediate and higher-value opportunity may lie in investing in R&D capabilities to develop bioequivalent products for export markets. Transitioning to Value-Added Product Development, i.e., shifting from a "low-cost manufacturing" mindset to focusing on value-added products, can increase competitiveness to meet the stringent regulatory requirements of the US, EU, and Latin American markets.

5. Selective API Development for Strategic Resilience

Bangladesh currently imports 85% of its API needs for USD 1.3 billion annually, exposing manufacturers to supply disruptions and price volatility. Establishing a *strategic API industry focusing on domestic high-value and niche APIs* could ensure another source of sustainable and cost-effective supply of raw materials, reducing external dependence to some extent. This approach avoids the pitfalls of attempting full-scale API substitution, which may not be economically viable.

Incentives:

Bangladesh offers a 7% subsidy on the exports of pharmaceutical products. Firms established between FY2019-20 and FY2023-24, are eligible for phased or partial tax exemption for 5 up to 10 years. There are 100% and 75% tax holidays for API producers depending on the molecules until 2032. Corporate tax exemptions, AIT free import are also applicable in this case.

4.3 Medical Equipment and Devices

Medical Device and Equipment Market is Valued at **US\$820 million** (2025 Projected)

[Healthcare and Medical Device, 2024. BIDA]

13% Compound Annual Growth Rate

Potential to become a **US\$ 3 billion market by 2030**

through establishing local manufacturing units for low risks devices and usable at home health assistive equipment.

[Inspira Extrapolation from Comparison with Similar Economy]

Key highlights of the Medical Equipment Industry

The demand for medical equipment and devices has been steadily growing in Bangladesh, with a CAGR of 13%. The sector is projected to reach US\$820 million by 2025. Historically, Bangladesh has been a net importer of medical equipment, and the existing manufacturers serve only 8% of the market. About 15-20 such manufacturing facilities are available, of which 4 can be considered large.

Import and Local Production of Medical Device (USD million)

Medical consumables production, e.g. disposable/ precision safety syringes, needles, blood bags, blood transfusion sets, cannula, and blood collection tubes, have a leading edge. In addition to consumables, Bangladesh manufactures a range of healthcare products, albeit on a limited scale. These include orthopedic devices (e.g., bone hooks, spinal retractors, and surgical drills), surgical sterilizers, hospital furniture, etc. The produced goods were intended to serve the healthcare channels or business entities. It is driven by a large demand surge from diagnostic centers and hospitals as these facilities increased six and four times respectively in the last 20 years and continue to grow onwards.

On the contrary, the direct-to-consumer segment of the medical equipment and device sector has been overlooked in the past. Enhanced purchasing power, increasing health consciousness, and complexity of non-communicable diseases are collectively driving the demand for low-risk medical devices, usable at-home equipment, and health assistive and monitoring devices. Middle-income families began to keep digital thermometers, blood pressure monitors, compressor nebulizers, glucometers, and pulse oximeters as household staples.

The medical equipment and device sector has the potential to grow to nearly US\$3 billion by 2030. This can be achieved by fulfilling the unmet needs of B2B channels, export channels, and the burgeoning B2C market. Although a few manufacturers began pregnancy kit and glucometer production, the majority of these less capital-intensive products (i.e., medical test kits/equipment) are imported despite representing the fastest CAGR of 32%. Other segments like Instrument/appliance as well as diagnostic and imaging devices combined, share about half of the total imports.

The dominance of imports provides the potential for manufacturers. As the market serves the huge demand, shifting the modality, from import-dependent to locally produced, the medical equipment sector can become completely built-up (CBU) to semi knocked down (SKD) or completely knocked down (CKD) manufacturing processes to address the domestic demand.

Not only does the production of equipment and devices hold investment potential, there is a need for certified medical devices and equipment at this stage of development. Supply of quality medical goods is essential for both the government's commitment to universal healthcare by 2030, as well as for export to foreign countries. While top-tier manufacturers are already producing WHO-compliant medical equipment, there is a need for unified and standardized products, which can only be ensured by third-party domestic institutions for product testing/certification in this sector.

Manufacturing and non-manufacturing wages are competitive in Bangladesh compared to China & India. With an average non-manufacturing wage of US\$ 370 per month, significantly lower than countries like China (US\$ 1301) and India (US\$ 734), businesses can benefit from reduced production costs, boosting profit margins (JETRO 2024).

Investment Opportunities

**Establishing
Manufacturing Unit**

**Establishing quality control
labs for testing and
certification of medical devices**

**Investing in equipment
leasing and revenue
sharing with hospitals**

The medical devices sector in Bangladesh presents significant investment opportunities, particularly in the manufacturing of consumables, surgical instruments, and medical appliances, driven by the increasing demand due to the country's growing healthcare needs. Investors can capitalize on this opportunity by setting up manufacturing units that focus on producing these high-demand items locally. Additionally, there is a need for quality control laboratories to test and certify medical devices, ensuring compliance with international standards, which presents another profitable avenue. The rise in non-communicable diseases (NCDs) further amplifies the demand for ICU/OT equipment, such as ventilators, ECG machines, and oxygen masks, creating a promising investment opportunity. Partnering with tertiary hospitals to support the expansion of critical care facilities can help meet the increasing demand for advanced medical equipment in Bangladesh. Investors can leverage Bangladesh's EPZs/EZs for low-risk device production. The sector is further bolstered by government incentives to reduce import reliance which can be leveraged by investors.

Incentives:

Bangladesh provides concessional import duties (SRO 11/AN/2021/06/Customs) for raw materials in medical equipment manufacturing. Post-COVID, full duty waivers apply to PPE, masks, and sanitizer materials. Exporters enjoy 50% tax exemption on export income, 0% VAT on shipped goods, and 10% cash incentives on export value. The government prioritizes local production to reduce import reliance (80% of devices imported) and offers EPZ/EZ benefits (tax holidays, duty-free machinery imports). BIDA's policies aim to elevate medical equipment exports to \$500M+ by 2030, targeting regional markets under preferential trade agreements.

4.4 Digital Healthcare

\$400 Million

It is the projected value of the overall digital healthcare and healthtech market in Bangladesh by 2028.

(Source: Inspira Extrapolation From Digital Healthcare Assessment Report, 2025)

~35–40% CAGR

Digital healthcare is one of the fastest growing subsector in healthcare since 2020 (projected)

(Source: Inspira Extrapolation, Healthtech Trends, Bangladesh Global Investment, BIDA)

~\$300M e-pharmacy

Pharmaceuticals being already a pioneer sector, The e-pharmacy segment is expected to grow to ~\$300m by 2028

(Source: Inspira Study on Digital Healthcare Sector of BD)

Major Segments in Digital Healthcare

Growth Enablers:

180m+

Registered mobile phone devices in Bangladesh

(Source: BTRC)

70%

Approximately 70.1% of the total household in both urban and Rural uses smart phone with high adoption rate

(Source: ICT first quarter survey 2024, BBS)

USD 10.36 Million raised by startups Since 2021

(Source: Bangladesh Startup Investment Reports 2021- 2023)

Fastest growing segment: E-pharmacy

(Source: Startup Bangladesh, Inspira Market research)

Key highlights of the Digital Healthcare Industry

Bangladesh's healthcare sector is embracing a digital revolution to tackle systemic issues and boost accessibility. With over 180 million mobile users and growing internet access, technologies like telemedicine and e-pharmacies are narrowing the urban-rural healthcare gap. Telehealth enables rural patients to consult specialists remotely, cutting travel needs, while e-pharmacies streamline medication delivery, especially for urban chronic disease patients.

The government's **Digital Healthcare Strategy 2023–2027** and Bangladesh Digital Health Architecture (BDHA) integrate AI-driven diagnostics, electronic health records (EHRs), and interoperable systems into public health. This is vital as 67% of deaths in Bangladesh are due to non-communicable diseases (NCDs), needing scalable, tech-enabled solutions.

Digital tools enhance efficiency and affordability. Cloud-based EHRs in startups and hospitals reduce prescription errors and improve data management, while AI aids early disease detection. Cost efficiency drives adoption, with Aggregator platforms offering remote services—prescriptions, follow-ups, and non-emergency lab tests—easing infrastructure strain and lowering costs.

Investment Opportunities

Bangladesh's digital healthcare sector offers favorable B2B investment opportunities across several high-growth segments. These include telemedicine, e-pharmacy, wearable devices, EMR, and EHR system software, AI integration in diagnostics, etc.

For example, Vietnam partnered with Roche in 2022 to test AI diagnostics, cutting approval time by 40%. Bangladesh can do the same through

foreign tech partnerships and flexible regulations for chronic disease solutions

Moreover, adopting a technology licensing model allows foreign technology developers to grant Bangladeshi healthcare providers the right to use proprietary tools for disease surveillance, diagnostics, or predictive analytics. These structured agreements let local partners, such as hospitals or diagnostic centers, integrate licensed technology into their operations, paying royalties or fees based on usage. For instance, foreign firms could license platforms for tuberculosis diagnosis or maternal health monitoring to Bangladeshi hospitals, aligning with the country's Digital Health Strategy. This model reduces upfront investment risks for foreign companies and promotes the rapid adoption of advanced technologies in a market that demands cost-effective healthcare solutions.

With Bangladesh's current infrastructure lacking in data interoperability (Score of 33.8 in access to communications infrastructure, significantly below the Global Average of 65.7), the healthcare sector faces challenges in sharing patient information efficiently between facilities. The need for seamless data integration across healthcare providers, therefore, is critical. Developing centralized healthcare databases & cloud-based data management systems offers substantial returns by streamlining patient care and enabling better disease tracking, real-time updates, and improved health outcomes, potentially positioning Bangladesh as a hub for digital health technologies in South Asia.

4.5 Medical Bio-technology

Key highlights of the Digital Healthcare Industry

The size of the global bio-economy market was valued at USD 1.55 trillion in 2024 and is projected to reach USD 4.61 trillion by 2034, growing at a CAGR of 11.5%. A significant share of this market will be captured by our regional peers such as India, Malaysia, Thailand, and Indonesia, where pharmaceutical, biotech, and life sciences ecosystems are rapidly developing. Bangladesh, with its well-established pharmaceutical industry and significant cost advantage for conducting clinical trials, can position itself as a key player in the regional bio-economy through strategic investments.

Potential Investment Opportunities

Bangladesh holds significant opportunities, especially in the fields of biopharmaceuticals, clinical trials, and biomedical devices. Bangladesh's biologics market, valued at USD 80 million in 2019, is poised for robust growth, with projections to reach USD 100 billion by 2030. This growth is driven by increasing demand for advanced treatments in NCDs, offering lucrative investment opportunities. However, expanding

Advantages for Bangladesh

Cost-Efficient Trials: Low-cost clinical trials with treatment-naïve patients Bangladesh is one of the most competitive locations for conducting clinical trials, reducing research costs for global pharma companies.

Biodiversity Hub: Rich ecosystems enable nutraceuticals, marine biotech, and herbal innovations.

Skilled Talentpool: 15,000+ graduates annually in biotechnology, pharmacy, chemistry, and other relevant life science disciplines, alongside 10,000+ medical graduates/annum

Market Gateway: Strategic access to 3B consumers market in South Asia-China via trade agreements.

Favorable geopolitical shift: Current geopolitical shifts in the US and EU have created opportunities for Bangladesh to attract investment from multinational biotech firms, as companies seek alternatives to China in genomics, CROs, and pharmaceutical supply chains.

Bangladesh's biosimilar manufacturing capacity and improving bioequivalence testing infrastructure will be essential to compete on a global scale. The global contract research organization (CRO) market is expected to reach USD 108 billion by 2032, and Bangladesh's large patient pool, English-speaking workforce, and growing network of trained clinical professionals position it as an attractive hub for clinical research. Expanding Bangladesh's CRO ecosystem and regulatory infrastructure will be critical to unlock this potential.

The biomedical devices and diagnostics sector offers another high-growth opportunity. The global market for biomedical devices is projected to grow from USD 640 billion in 2024 to USD 1.14 trillion by 2034. Bangladesh, with its increasing demand for affordable medical devices, can tap into this market by leveraging its low production costs and existing pharmaceutical expertise. Key areas for investment include medical imaging, diagnostic kits, and AI-driven healthcare tools, positioning Bangladesh as a competitive player in the global medical device manufacturing sector.

Bangladesh's Biopharmaceutical Vision: Strategic Projects to Catalyze Innovation and Post-TRIPS Readiness

The proposed Laboratory Animal House (under the Ministry of Fisheries & Livestock) and the Vaccines, Therapeutics, and Diagnostics (VTD) Manufacturing Project (funded by ADB under EDCL)—currently in the pre-development (PDPP) and design stages—will establish Bangladesh as a transformative hub for biopharmaceutical innovation, attracting significant foreign direct investment (FDI). Once operational, the Laboratory Animal House will address the global bottleneck in preclinical trials by providing world-class infrastructure for ethical, compliant testing across species, enabling multinational firms to expedite drug discovery while sharing intellectual property with Bangladesh through collaborative research. Concurrently, the VTD project will modernize vaccine and biologics manufacturing with WHO-GMP-certified facilities, advanced R&D centers, and strengthened regulatory frameworks, creating end-to-end capabilities from drug development to production.

These initiatives will strategically position Bangladesh to transition into the post-TRIPS era post-2033, when its pharmaceutical patent exemption expires. By prioritizing indigenous R&D, fostering IP generation through global partnerships, and scaling advanced manufacturing, the projects will enable a shift from generic drug dependency to high-value innovation, ensuring compliance with future IP regimes. Enhanced regulatory transparency, cost-efficient infrastructure, and a skilled workforce trained in cutting-edge technologies will mitigate investor risks, while Bangladesh's access to South Asian markets will offer strategic advantages for FDI. Multinational firms diversifying supply chains or seeking collaborative ventures in biologics and pandemic preparedness will leverage this integrated ecosystem, combining preclinical testing and production under one jurisdiction.

Bangladesh is stepping into a new horizon of economic and industrial expansion. It is enhancing policies to strengthen its international market presence. Given its strategic geo-economic position, the country has the potential to become a global destination for drug development. Bangladesh's biotech sector has immense potential, and targeted therapy in biomedicine could be a game-changer. I believe we have untapped possibilities with a particular focus on biomedicine. Adequate local & international investment will enable not only National Biosecurity but also drive innovation, playing critical roles in creating a knowledge-based society.

Dr. Umme Salma Zohora
Professor
Department of Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering
Jahangirnagar University

5

Health Insurance: An Untapped Market

Private insurance coverage in the country is still in the budding stage, with only 2.5% of the population possessing health insurance. Most of this proportion is constituted of corporate plans for white collar employees.

About 74% of healthcare costs are paid out-of-pocket. The proportion is comparatively higher than the countries like India, Indonesia, and Vietnam.

On the other hand, the government wishes to cover 100% of the population under Universal Health Coverage for primary-level healthcare support. This was aimed to be achieved by 2032 through achieving 16 indicators. Although the progress is steady but remains ambitious. Therefore, both public and private level insurance coverage remains comparatively low despite increasing demand from the middle and affluent classes.

Insurance providers used to be more intuition driven while designing and promoting health insurance products due to the lack of personalized data on the insurers.

Out-Of-Pocket Expenditure As Proportion of Total Healthcare Costs (%)

However, with the advent and propagation of digital healthcare aggregators, the problem regarding data dearth is waning. Digital healthcare platforms present an opportunity to integrate insurance products with telemedicine, health monitoring apps, and e-pharmacy services. By leveraging an aggregator platform, insurers can offer seamless coverage bundled with digital health services, enabling users to manage claims, consultations, and medications in one unified system, enhancing convenience and affordability for consumers while expanding access to essential healthcare services. Some traditional insurance providers in Bangladesh are now collaborating with aggregator platforms by pooling their data resources.

This presents a good base for an investment opportunity. With competitive offerings, investors can expect a high return on investment in this sector. The stake and modality for the health insurance investment can vary. It can range from 100% foreign ownership by the likes of AIA, Manulife, and FWD in Vietnam, or majority stake ownership akin to Allianz, Prudential, and Sun Life in Indonesia.

With the right products and distribution channels, investors can tap into a rapidly expanding market, benefiting from the increasing demand for healthcare protection and the rise of digital platforms to reach more consumers.

Industry Voices

Bangladesh's healthcare market continues to grow at around 10% annually. With increasing healthcare expenditure, a young population, urban-rural care disparities, and high mobile penetration, demand for telemedicine and digital health services is rising rapidly. These conditions create fertile ground for innovative, tech-enabled healthcare models, making the digital health sector a promising area with significant investment potential for forward-thinking healthcare companies.

-Yutaro Yokokawa, CEO, Miup Inc

Bangladesh's healthcare sector offers significant investment opportunities driven by rapid economic growth, a rising middle class, and increasing demand for quality services. The market is projected to grow 10% annually. However, gaps in medical expertise force 200,000 patients abroad yearly for advanced care. Meanwhile, Japan's aging society has skilled acute-care professionals seeking overseas opportunities. Bridging this gap can enhance Bangladesh's healthcare system, curb medical outflows, and foster mutually beneficial collaboration with Japan and other developed nations.

-Futoshi Kono, Director, Ship International Hospital

Bangladesh's healthcare market holds an untapped demand of over USD 20 billion – a clear signal that the sector is ripe for transformative investment. But success here won't come from simply importing foreign doctors or management practices. What the country needs is robust infrastructure, capable local management, stronger monitoring systems, and above all, the trust of patients. The domestic private sector, empowered by modern systems and accountable governance, is the key to unlocking this massive opportunity.

-A M Shamim, Founder & Managing Director of Labaid Group

Access to healthcare is a vital factor in enhancing a country's social development. This is why healthcare investment stands as one of the four cornerstones of IFU's strategy for driving meaningful impact. IFU's most recent healthcare investment in AKS Khan Pharmaceuticals and their pharmacy-first primary care model, combined with their comprehensive diagnostic solutions, will extend quality healthcare services to millions more patients. Through this investment, we are committing to a healthier and more prosperous future for Bangladesh. Concurrently, we view this investment as financially robust, promising returns over time. This initiative exemplifies the kind of impact investment that has been IFU's specialty since 1967 and will continue to be a part of our efforts, contributing to the green transition as well as economic and social development in Bangladesh.

-Lars Bo Bertram, CEO, International Funds for Developing Countries (IFU)

Bangladesh presents a unique and timely opportunity for digital healthcare investment. With a young, tech-savvy population, rising health consciousness, and rapid adoption of mobile technologies, the country is ready for scalable, tech-enabled healthcare solutions. The gaps in traditional healthcare delivery open the door for innovation across telemedicine, digital pharmacies, diagnostics, and health data infrastructure. It's a high-growth sector with the potential for deep social impact - both for investors and for the millions who stand to benefit from better, faster, and more affordable care.

-Yawar Mehboob, Co-founder & CSO, Arogga

Bangladesh's potential to nurture a "bio-hub" is tremendous. With its thriving biotech research, the nation has seen breakthroughs such as OxyJet, an innovative oxygen delivery system, and paper-based biosensors for diagnostic purposes, which have garnered international recognition. Leading research institutions and private companies are fostering an environment ripe for growth. The country's further focus on indigenous R&D, biopharmaceutical innovations, and collaborations with global partners will position it as a hub for biotechnology and life sciences, making it an exciting destination for future investments in the sector.

*-Shoeb Ahmed, Coordinator, Applied Bioengineering Research Incubator (ABRI)
Professor & Head, Department of Chemical Engineering, BUET*

In Bangladesh, the future of healthcare lies in digital transformation. Every innovation that reduces friction and improves access to quality care presents a strong investment opportunity. With rising connectivity, the adoption of AI, and favorable demographics, the country is uniquely positioned for growth in healthtech and digital healthcare. Now is the time to invest where technology meets human need.

-Sajid Rahman, Managing Partner, myAsiaVC

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Annex

Navigating the Regulatory Process for Setting Up a Healthcare Business

Hospital Licensing Process Flow Chart

List of Licenses Required for Hospital/ Diagnostic Centers:

1. NOC from Local Government Authority (Chairman/Commissioner)
2. NOC from DGHS
3. Trade License from City Corporation
4. Incorporation License from RJSC
5. Investment Approval from BIDA
6. Fire License from FSCD
7. Waste Management License from PRISM
8. Environment License from DOE (ETP, STP, WTP)
9. E-TIN & VAT Enlistment from NBR
10. IRC (if Import Required) from CCI&E
11. "A" Category Trade Body Membership (BPMCA/BPCDOA) is required for CCI&E
12. Drug License for Pharmacy from DGDA
13. Hospital Diagnostic License from DGHS
14. Radiation Safety License from BAEC
15. Electricity License from DESCO/DPDC
16. Solar Panel for DESCO License Depends on Electricity Load Capacity Requirement 10%
17. Water Supply License from WASA
18. Narcotic License from DNC
19. Site Clearance from DOE for Building Construction
20. Labour License from DOL after Opening and getting all approval Lima Portal

Digital Healthcare Licensing Process Flow Chart

List of Licenses Required for Digital Healthcare:

1. NOC from Ministry of Health (DG Health)
2. RJSC Application for Name Clearance & Incorporation
3. Apply for Trade License (DSCC/DNCC, Municipalities, Union Parishad) Depends on Office Locations)
4. E-TIN & BIN Registration from NBR
5. Apply for BIDA Approval for Project Registration & Work Permit for Foreign Nationals
6. Apply for DGDA Approval for Providing Medical Consultation
7. Apply for BTRC Approval for Digital Services
8. Apply for Pharmacy Council for Pharmacy Licenses
9. Apply for DBID (Digital Business Identity) (Apply Link: <https://www.mygov.bd/service/?id=BDGS-1636617652>)
10. Apply for e-CAB Memberships (E-Commerce Association of Business)

Pharmaceuticals/Medical Equipment Manufacturing Plant Licensing Process Flow Chart

List of Licenses Required for Pharmaceuticals/ Medical Equipment Manufacturing sector:

1. Name Clearance & Certificate of Incorporation from RJSC
2. Project Registration with BIDA Bangladesh Investment Development Authority (BIDA)
3. Ad-hoc IRC/ BIDA Recommendation Bangladesh Investment Development Authority (BIDA)
4. Membership from Bangladesh Association of Pharmaceuticals Industries (BAPI)
5. Approval of Foreign Loan Bangladesh Investment Development Authority (BIDA)
6. Construction Certificate RAJUK/CDA/KDA
7. Approval of Factory Plan Department of Inspection for Factories and Establishments (DIFE)
8. Certificate of Registration of Factories and Establishment Department of Inspection for Factories and Establishments (DIFE)
9. Bonded Warehouse License Customs Bond Commissionerate (CBC)
10. Copyright Registration Copyright Office
11. Environmental Clearance Certificate Department of Environment (DOE)
12. Explosives Licenses Department of Explosives
13. Export Registration Certificate (ERC) Office of the Chief Controller of Imports & Exports (CCI&E)
14. Fire License Fire Service and Civil Defence (FS&CD)
15. Import Registration Certificate (IRC) Office of the Chief Controller of Imports & Exports (CCI&E)
16. API Import for manufacturing of Medicine
17. Quality Certification Mark Bangladesh Standard and Testing Institution (BSTI)
18. Registration Certificate from Inspector of Boiler Office of the Chief Inspector of Boiler (CIOB)
19. Registration Certificate of Designs Department of Patent, Design and Trade Marks (DPDT)
20. Registration Certificate of Patent Department of Patent, Design and Trade Marks (DPDT)
21. Tax Identification Number (TIN) National Board of Revenue (NBR)
22. VAT Registration National Board of Revenue (NBR)
23. Trade License All City Corporations, Municipalities & Union Parishads
24. Trade Marks Registration Department of Patents, Designs & Trademarks (DPDT)
25. Work Permit for Foreign Nationals BIDA and BEPZA
26. DESCO/DPDC License for Factory Electricity

List of Licenses Required for Biotech company:

Similar to "Pharmaceuticals" except for the following:

Ethical Approval for Clinical Research/Trials

- Obtain approval to conduct clinical research and trials on human subjects. Bangladesh Medical Research Council (BMRC).
- Prepared By: Md Rajib Hossain, CFO (Healthcare Professional)
- Obtain approval from an Ethics Review Committee (IRB) that assesses the ethical aspects of the study.
- Ensure informed consent is obtained from trial participants.

Clinical Trial Authorization

Submit an application for Clinical Trial Authorization to DGDA, which includes:

- Clinical trial protocol, Details of the investigational drug or medical device.
- Data from previous studies (if any).
- Ensure compliance with Good Clinical Practice (GCP) and International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines.
- Obtain clinical trial approval from the DGDA before initiating trials.

Research and Development (R&D) Licensing

- Apply for an R&D License to the Ministry of Science and Technology to conduct research activities.
- The research must comply with ethical standards and biosafety regulations.
- Ensure the R&D facility meets safety standards for handling biohazardous materials (if applicable).

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